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of **EXPRESSION**
A Creative Folio

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The Silent Cry

He sits in the back row,
eyes tracing the floor.
His smile is practiced,
his silence is too loud.

I ask, Are you alright?
He answers with a shrug.
Words escape him,
however, the weight does not.

Homework is untouched,
not from laziness
but from battles
no one else can see.

Teachers mark the grade,
peers mark the absence,
yet no one marks
the ache he hides.

I sit closer,
offering space,
a chance for truth
to find its voice.

Not all pain shouts.
Some fold themselves neatly
into silence,
waiting to be found.